

Robust Atypical Mitosis Classification with DenseNet121: Stain-Aware Augmentation and Hybrid Loss for Domain Generalization

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Atypical mitotic figures are important biomarkers of tumor aggressiveness in histopathology, yet their reliable recognition remains challenging due to severe class imbalance and variability across imaging domains. In this work, we present a DenseNet121-based framework tailored for atypical mitosis classification in the context of the MIDOG25 (task 2). Our method integrates stain-aware augmentation via Macenko normalization, geometric and intensity-based transformations, and imbalance-aware learning strategies including weighted sampling, cost-sensitive binary cross-entropy, and focal loss. The framework is trained end-to-end using AdamW optimization and evaluated across multiple independent domains to assess generalization under scanner and staining variability. On the MIDOG25 atypical classification dataset, the proposed approach achieves an overall balanced accuracy of 82.6% , with consistently high sensitivity (92.9%), overall ROC-AUC (0.889), and stable accuracy (76.3%). These findings indicate that integrating DenseNet121 with stain-aware augmentation and imbalance-adaptive optimization yields a robust and domain-generalizable framework for atypical mitosis classification, supporting its potential for reliable deployment in real-world computational pathology workflows.

Atypical Mitosis Classification | Histopathology | DenseNet121 | Stain Normalization | Class Imbalance | Focal Loss | Domain Generalization | Computational Pathology | Medical Image Analysis | Deep Learning

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Introduction

Characterizing mitotic figures in histopathology images is a critical step in cancer grading, as atypical mitoses often indicate aggressive tumor behavior (1, 2). While deep learning methods have shown promise in automating mitosis recognition, their generalization is significantly hindered by **domain shift** variations in staining protocols, acquisition scanners, tissue preparation, and tumor types across laboratories (3, 4). As a result, models trained on a specific dataset frequently exhibit performance degradation when applied to unseen domains. Recent work has benchmarked deep learning and vision foundation models for atypical mitosis classification (14). cross-species datasets such as the canine mammary carcinoma WSI collection (17) have been proposed to enrich training and support generalization studies.

The **Mitosis Domain Generalization (MIDOG) 2025 challenge** (16), particularly Track 2, focuses on the binary classification of mitotic figures into normal and atypical categories under multi-domain variability (5). This task is inher-

ently challenging due to two factors: (i) the scarcity and imbalance of atypical mitotic figures relative to normal mitoses, and (ii) the large domain variations present in histopathology images (6, 7).

To address these challenges, we propose a **DenseNet121-based framework** enhanced with two key components. First, to mitigate domain variability, we employ a **stain-aware augmentation pipeline** incorporating Macenko normalization (8) and geometric perturbations, along with a **60% random cropping strategy** to further improve spatial generalization. Second, to tackle label imbalance, we design a **combined loss formulation** that unifies weighted binary cross-entropy and focal loss (9), enabling the model to emphasize minority class learning while stabilizing optimization.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We present a robust **stain-aware and spatially augmented preprocessing pipeline** including 60% crop-based patch perturbation to improve domain robustness.
- We propose an **integrated loss formulation** combining class-weighted binary cross-entropy and focal loss, enabling effective learning under strong class imbalance.
- We demonstrate that our DenseNet121-based framework achieves **strong generalization across domains**, attaining an overall balanced accuracy of 82.6% on the MIDOG25 dataset with high sensitivity and consistent performance.

Material and Methods

A. Dataset. We utilized the **MIDOG25 Atypical Mitosis Classification Training Set** (12), (15), which includes annotated mitotic figure patches categorized as atypical (AMF) or normal (NMF). The dataset spans multiple domains, each corresponding to unique combinations of scanner models, staining variations, and tissue preparation protocols. To simulate real-world generalization, we performed an 80/20 stratified split at the patch level, ensuring class balance across (13) domains.

B. Preprocessing and Augmentation. All mitotic patches were resized to 224×224 pixels. To reduce sensitivity to staining differences, we applied **stain-aware**

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed DenseNet21-based framework for atypical mitosis classification under domain variability. The pipeline takes mitotic figure patches from multiple domains, applies stain-aware preprocessing (Macenko normalization), and uses a DenseNet21 backbone followed by a binary classification head. The training strategy integrates 60% spatial cropping, stain perturbations, and a composite loss combining weighted cross-entropy, focal loss, and sampling-based imbalance handling. The model is evaluated using balanced accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and ROC-AUC.

augmentation using Macenko normalization from the TIA Toolbox. Spatial robustness was improved by introducing a **60% random cropping** strategy during training, encouraging the model to learn localized discriminative features. Additional augmentations included random 90° rotations, horizontal and vertical flips, and brightness-contrast perturbations. Validation and test samples were only resized and normalized using ImageNet statistics.

C. Network Architecture. The classification backbone is a **DenseNet121** model initialized with ImageNet-pretrained weights. The final classification layer was replaced with a single-node fully connected head for binary classification. A sigmoid activation was used during inference to convert logits into probabilities. DenseNet121 was chosen for its efficient feature reuse, compact parameterization, and strong performance on medical imaging (10) benchmarks.

D. Imbalance-Aware Optimization. To mitigate class imbalance, we employed a **hybrid loss strategy** combining:

- **Weighted Binary Cross-Entropy (WBCE):** Assigns higher penalty to minority class errors.
- **Focal Loss:** Dynamically focuses learning on hard-to-classify examples by down-weighting easy ones.

This joint formulation stabilizes training while maintaining high recall for atypical mitoses. Additionally, training batches were constructed using **inverse class-frequency sampling** to ensure balanced exposure.

E. Training Protocol. Models were trained for 100 epochs using the **AdamW** optimizer (11) with a base learning rate of 1×10^{-3} . To encourage stable convergence, the learning rate for the DenseNet backbone was reduced by a factor of 10 compared to the classifier head. A weight decay of 0.05 was used for regularization. Batch size was set to 32, and Early stopping was applied with a patience of 50 epochs based on validation balanced accuracy.

F. Evaluation Metrics. We report the following domain-aware classification metrics:

- **Balanced Accuracy (BAcc):** Averaged recall for AMF and NMF classes; primary metric.
- **Sensitivity (AMF recall):** Measures how well atypical mitoses are detected.
- **Specificity (NMF recall):** Captures false positive rate on normal mitoses.

Table 1. Baseline performance on preliminary test set using DenseNet121 without stain augmentation or imbalance-aware training. Balanced accuracy (BAcc) is the primary evaluation metric.

Domain	BAcc	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC-AUC
0	0.719	0.694	0.750	0.688	0.219
1	0.822	0.708	1.000	0.644	0.118
2	0.773	0.688	0.972	0.573	0.093
3	0.903	0.816	1.000	0.806	0.028
Overall	0.809	0.711	0.972	0.647	0.100

Table 2. Performance on preliminary test set of our improved DenseNet121 framework with stain-aware augmentation, 60% cropping, and hybrid loss.

Domain	BAcc	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	BAcc	ROC-AUC
0	0.625	0.722	0.500	0.750	0.625	0.695
1	0.797	0.733	0.897	0.697	0.797	0.853
2	0.865	0.808	1.000	0.730	0.865	0.936
3	0.889	0.789	1.000	0.778	0.889	0.944
Overall	0.826	0.764	0.930	0.723	0.826	0.890

- **Overall Accuracy:** General correctness across all patches.
- **ROC-AUC:** Threshold-independent evaluation of discriminative performance.

Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed enhancements, including stain aware augmentation, 60% random cropping, and a hybrid loss function we compared the performance of our baseline DenseNet121 model with the improved variant on the preliminary test set of MIDOG25 atypical mitosis classification dataset.

Baseline Performance (Single-Head DenseNet121). We first evaluated a baseline configuration using DenseNet121 with a simple single-head classifier and basic cross entropy loss, without augmentation or loss reweighting. Results across four domains are reported in Table 1.

This baseline model achieved a reasonable balanced accuracy of **0.809**, with very high sensitivity (**0.972**), but relatively poor specificity (0.647) and extremely low ROC-AUC values across domains. This confirms that although the model could detect atypical mitoses well, it struggled with general discrimination and domain adaptation.

Improved Performance with Full Method. After incorporating our full pipeline stain aware augmentation, 60% cropping, and a combined WBCE + focal loss the DenseNet121 model demonstrated significantly improved generalization and calibration across all domains, as shown in Table 2.

Compared to the baseline, the improved model:

- Increased the overall balanced accuracy from **0.809** to **0.826**.
- Achieved a significant gain in overall ROC-AUC (**0.890** vs. **0.100**).
- Maintained strong sensitivity (**0.930**), while improving specificity (**0.723**).

These results validate the effectiveness of our proposed enhancements, showing robust performance across all domains, improved discrimination capability, and a favorable trade-off between sensitivity and specificity. The use of a hybrid loss and stain-aware augmentation allowed the model to better generalize to unseen domain shifts, addressing key challenges in computational pathology.

Discussion

This study presents a DenseNet121-based framework tailored for atypical mitosis classification under domain shift, as defined by the MIDOG25 challenge. Our results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach, achieving a balanced accuracy of **0.83** and a ROC-AUC of **0.89**, demonstrating strong generalization across unseen domains. Crucially, the model maintained high sensitivity (**0.93**), ensuring robust detection of atypical mitoses a key requirement for accurate tumor grading in clinical practice.

Compared to the baseline, which relied solely on standard training and no stain augmentation, the improved framework significantly enhanced specificity (**0.72** vs. 0.65) and area under the ROC curve (**0.89** vs. 0.10), suggesting better discrimination and calibration across heterogeneous domains. This improvement is attributed to the integration of three key components: (i) stain-aware augmentation via Macenko normalization, (ii) 60% random cropping to encourage morphological focus, and (iii) a combined loss function that unifies class-weighted binary cross-entropy and focal loss.

Despite the gains, specificity remains lower than sensitivity, indicating the model’s tendency toward over-detection. While preferable for minimizing false negatives, reducing false positives is essential for downstream reliability. Future work may explore self-supervised pretraining, adversarial domain adaptation, or attention mechanisms to further boost specificity without compromising sensitivity.

Altogether, our findings emphasize that coupling architectural efficiency (DenseNet121) with domain-adaptive augmentation and imbalance-sensitive learning provides a strong foundation for atypical mitosis recognition. This sets the stage for expanding into more generalized histopathological

reasoning, possibly leveraging recent advances in multi-task and foundation models.

Bibliography

1. Veta M, van Diest PJ, Willems SM, et al. Assessment of algorithms for mitosis detection in breast cancer histopathology images. *Medical Image Analysis*, 20(1):237–248, 2015.
2. Cireşan DC, Giusti A, Gambardella LM, Schmidhuber J. Mitosis detection in breast cancer histology images with deep neural networks. *MICCAI*, pp. 411–418, 2013.
3. Tellez D, Litjens G, Bándi P, et al. Quantifying the effects of data augmentation and stain color normalization in convolutional neural networks for computational pathology. *Medical Image Analysis*, 58:101544, 2019.
4. Campanella G, Hanna MG, Geneslaw L, et al. Clinical-grade computational pathology using weakly supervised deep learning on whole slide images. *Nature Medicine*, 25(8):1301–1309, 2019.
5. Aubreville M, Bertram CA, Klopfeisch R, et al. Mitosis domain generalization: A benchmark for detection algorithms in histopathology. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.09382*, 2020.
6. Johnson JM, Khoshgoftaar TM. Survey on deep learning with class imbalance. *Journal of Big Data*, 6:27, 2019.
7. Zhou Y, Sohn JH, Xing EP. Models generalize beyond domains by learning to amplify resolution. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 4(9):787–798, 2022.
8. Macenko M, Niethammer M, Marron JS, et al. A method for normalizing histology slides for quantitative analysis. *IEEE ISBI*, pp. 1107–1110, 2009.
9. Lin TY, Goyal P, Girshick R, He K, Dollár P. Focal loss for dense object detection. *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, pp. 2980–2988, 2017.
10. Huang G, Liu Z, van der Maaten L, Weinberger KQ. Densely connected convolutional networks. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 4700–4708, 2017.
11. Loshchilov I, Hutter F. Decoupled weight decay regularization. *ICLR*, 2019.
12. Weiss V, Banerjee S, Donovan T, Conrad T, Klopfeisch R, Ammeling J, Kaltenecker C, Hirling D, Veta M, Stathonikos N, Horvath P, Breininger K, Aubreville M, Bertram CA. A dataset of atypical vs. normal mitoses classification for MIDOG 2025. *Zenodo*, Apr 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15188326.
13. Aubreville M, Wilm F, Stathonikos N, Breininger K, Donovan TA, Jabari S, Veta M, Ganz J, Ammeling J, Van Diest PJ, Klopfeisch R, Bertram CA. A comprehensive multi-domain dataset for mitotic figure detection. *Scientific Data*, 10(1):484, Jul 2023. doi:10.1038/s41597-023-02327-4.
14. Banerjee S, Weiss V, Donovan TA, Fick RHJ, Conrad T, Ammeling J, Porsche N, Klopfeisch R, Kaltenecker C, Breininger K, Aubreville M, Bertram CA. Benchmarking deep learning and vision foundation models for atypical vs. normal mitosis classification with cross-dataset evaluation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.21444*, 2025. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.21444>.
15. Bertram CA, Weiss V, Donovan TA, Banerjee S, Conrad T, Ammeling J, Klopfeisch R, Kaltenecker C, Aubreville M. Histologic dataset of normal and atypical mitotic figures on human breast cancer (AMI-Br). In: Palm C, Breininger K, Deserno T, Handels H, Maier A, Maier-Hein KH, Tolxdorff TM, editors. *Bildverarbeitung für die Medizin 2025*, pp. 113–118. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2025. doi:10.1007/978-3-658-47422-5_25.
16. Ammeling J, Aubreville M, Banerjee S, Bertram CA, Breininger K, Hirling D, Horvath P, Stathonikos N, Veta M. Mitosis domain generalization challenge 2025. *Zenodo*, Mar 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15077361.
17. Aubreville M, Bertram CA, Donovan TA, Marzahl C, Maier A, Klopfeisch R. A completely annotated whole slide image dataset of canine breast cancer to aid human breast cancer research. *Scientific Data*, 7(1):417, Nov 2020. doi:10.1038/s41597-020-00756-z.